

In-vitro and *In-silico* Investigation of Chalcone's Therapeutic Potential: Antimicrobial, Cytotoxic (MTT Assay), and Molecular Dynamics Studies

Anaglit Catherine Paul^a, Jayasudha Nehru^a, Yogeswaran Velmurgan^b, J. Beaula^a,
Jose Kavitha Savaridasson^a, Venkatachalam Rajakannan^b, Madhukar Hemamalini^{a*}

a Department of Chemistry, Mother Teresa Women's University, Kodaikanal, Tamil Nadu

b Centre of advanced study in Crystallography and Biophysics, University of Madras, Chennai, India

Received: Mar 2, 2025

Accepted: Mar 27, 2026

Published: Mar 31, 2026

Abstract - This study investigates the biological activity of two chalcone compounds, BDP and BMP. Both showed significant antibacterial (*E. coli*, *S. aureus*) and antifungal (*C. albicans*) activity. BDP was especially potent against *C. albicans*. Favourable pharmacokinetics were predicted (SWISS ADME). Both compounds demonstrated cytotoxicity against MDA-MB-231 breast cancer cells, with similar IC₅₀ values (~53 μM). Molecular docking and MD simulations revealed high, stable binding affinity to the TP53 protein (-6.9 and -6.8 kcal/mol, respectively), suggesting a promising mechanism for anticancer development.

Keywords: Chalcones; antimicrobial activity; MTT assay; Molecular Docking; Molecular Dynamics

I. INTRODUCTION

Globally, cancer is the second greatest cause of death after heart disease, and over 70% of all cancer deaths have taken place in developing and underdeveloped Nations [1, 2]. The number of deaths from cancer is steadily increasing, with an estimated 12 million deaths from cancer worldwide in 2030 [3]. Breast cancer is the most prevalent cancer in women, second only to skin cancer, and the second most common cause of cancer-related deaths in women, after lung cancer [4,5]. Today, there are several therapeutic approaches for treating cancer, such as radiation and chemotherapy. However, the majority of the time, the growth of drug-resistant tumors and the systemic toxicity of the chemotherapeutic medicines restrict the favorable outcomes. Therefore, the discovery of new anticancer drugs to treat (breast) cancer is always needed. Numerous heterocyclic and non-heterocyclic scaffolds have recently been studied for their ability to inhibit the growth of different tumor cell lines [6–14]. Among them, chalcones are one of the most promising substances with pharmacological and anticancer properties. Numerous plant species include chalcones, structurally common members of the flavonoid family [15, 16]. These are chemically known as 1, 3-diphenyl-2-propen-1-one and have been shown to exhibit a variety of biological actions, such as antimalarial, anti-inflammatory, anti-leishmanial, and modification of P-glycoprotein-mediated multidrug resistance [17–22]. Most naturally occurring chalcones, including butein, licochalcone-A, isoliquiritigenin, xanthoangelol, and flavokawain A, are hydroxylated. Various cancer cells have been demonstrated to halt cell cycle progression, trigger apoptosis, and prevent tumor growth and metastasis [23–27]. Several investigations have shown chalcones have anti-proliferative effects on breast cancer cell lines [28–30]. Motivated by these results and our desire to research new heterocyclic chalcones for anticancer activity [31, 32].

The structures of two chalcone compounds, 1-(4-Bromo-phenyl)-3-(2,4-dimethoxy-phenyl)-propenone (BDP) and 1-(4-Bromo-phenyl)-3-(5-methylfuran-2-yl)-propenone (BMP), were successfully confirmed by single-crystal X-ray diffraction analysis in our laboratory. Building upon previous studies that highlighted their material science applications, the present work is dedicated to investigating their biological activity. Motivated by these findings, this study will focus on exploring the anticancer potential of these two heterocyclic chalcone compounds..

II. EXPERIMENTAL WORK

A. Synthesis of Chalcones

The synthesis of chalcone BDP and BMP were carried out by dissolving a mixture of 4-bromoacetophenone (0.01 mol), 2,4-dimethoxybenzaldehyde (0.01 mol) and 5-methyl furfural (0.01 mol) in methanol (20 mL). A catalytic amount of 20% NaOH (5 mL) was added drop wise to the solution, which was then stirred vigorously for 5–6 hours at room temperature. The resulting crude solid was filtered, washed several times with distilled water, and recrystallized from acetone to yield the pure chalcones. The general schematic diagram of the synthesized chalcones, BDP and BMP, are shown in Scheme 1. The synthetic procedure and crystal structures of these compounds have been previously reported from our laboratory [33].

Scheme 1: General Schematic diagram of BDP and BMP

Whereas, X– Br; R' - 2,4dimethoxybenzaldehyde; R''- 5 methyl furfural

B. In-vitro studies of Chalcone compounds

Antibacterial activity

Antibacterial activities of the tested sample were evaluated using the well diffusion method on nutrient agar. The bacterial strains *E. coli* (ATCC 10536) and *S. aureus* (ATCC 25923) were used for the antibacterial assay. Nutrient agar plates were inoculated with 100 μ L of a grown bacterial culture, which was then spread-plated under aseptic conditions using a glass L-rod. Then, a 9 mm round well was made in each plate using an aseptic stainless-steel cork borer. Different concentrations (25–100 μ L) of the antimicrobial agent solution were introduced into the wells, and the plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. After incubation, the zone of inhibition was measured and reported in millimeters (mm). The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) was considered the lowest concentration that inhibited the growth of the respective microorganism. All assays were performed in triplicate. The extracts were dissolved in distilled water, and Chloramphenicol was used as a positive control.

Antifungal Activity

Fungal cell lines (procured from ATCC) were cultured in YPD broth and incubated overnight at 37 °C with shaking at 120 RPM. Cell viability was confirmed by plating. The YPD broth and agar media were sterilized by autoclaving. Sterile YPD agar was poured into Petri dishes and allowed to solidify. A lawn of *Candida albicans* (ATCC 90028) was then created on the agar surface by spread-plating. Using a sterile well cutter, wells were aseptically created in the agar. One hundred microliters of the dissolved samples, prepared at various concentrations, were then added to the wells. The plates were incubated at 37 °C for 24 hours. Antifungal activity was assessed by measuring the zone of inhibition in millimeters (mm). All assays were performed in triplicate. The samples were dissolved in distilled water, and Fluconazole was used as a positive control.

MTT Assay

A monolayer cell culture was trypsinized, and the cell count was adjusted to 1.0×10^5 cells/mL using the appropriate growth medium containing 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS). One hundred microliters of this diluted cell suspension, containing 5,000 cells/well, was then added to each well of a 96-well micro titer plate. After 24 hours, when a partial monolayer had formed, the supernatant was flicked off and the cells were washed once with fresh medium. One hundred microliters of the test drug at various concentrations were then added to the wells containing the partial monolayer. The plates were incubated at 37°C in a 5% CO₂ atmosphere for 24 hours. Following this incubation, the test solutions were discarded and 100 μ L of MTT solution (5 mg MTT in 10 mL of PBS) was added to each well. The plates were then incubated for 4 hours at 37°C in a 5% CO₂ atmosphere. The supernatant was removed, and 100 μ L of DMSO was added to each well. The plates were gently shaken to

solubilize the formazan crystals that had formed. The absorbance was measured using a micro plate reader at a wavelength of 590 nm. The percentage growth inhibition was calculated using a specified formula, and the half maximal inhibitory concentration (IC₅₀) values were generated from the dose-response curves for each cell line.

Calculating Inhibition:

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = 100 - (\text{OD of sample} / \text{OD of Control}) \times 100.$$

C. *In-silico studies of Chalcone compounds*

Swiss ADME predictions:

The standard pharmacokinetics (Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism and Excretion) and drug-likeness were determined for the estimation of the drug-likeness and pharmacokinetics parameters in the field of the drug discovery process. Both the crystal structures were drawn on Marvin JS software in 2-D structure format and converted into SMILES using Open babe online tool. The various physicochemical features and pharmacokinetic descriptors such as Log P, topological polar surface area (TPSA), number of hydrogen bond donors (HBD), acceptors (HBA), and number of rotatable bonds were calculated for BDP and BMP through the online tool Swiss-ADME (<http://swissadme.ch/>) [34-36].

Molecular Docking:

Molecular docking is a computational strategy biologists use to explore the interaction between enzymes and ligands. The drug target was determined to be TP53 in PDB ID 3ZME (<https://www.rcsb.org/structure/3ZME>) [37-38] based on data from the literature. The PDB ID 3ZME, which has a Y220C mutant TP53 core domain and a small molecule stabilizer (QC5) to stabilize the mutation, was at a high resolution of 1.35 Å. The 3ZME was then prepared for molecular docking using pymol [39]. The preparation steps include removing water molecules, small molecules, and chain B from 3ZME. Hydrogens and Kollman charges were added to the prepared 3ZME and converted to pdbqt format through Autodock [40]. The Autodock Vina in Pyrx 0.8 [41] has been used to perform molecular docking experiments. For docking investigations in Pyrx 0.8, the protein's generated pdbqt file was utilized. The molecules were loaded, and the make ligand option was selected to convert it to pdbqt format. The grid box has been fixed in the active site where the small molecule (QC5) stabiliser interacts with 3ZME. The active site residues are PHE109, LEU257, LEU145, VAL157, VAL147, ASP148, SER149, ASP228, THR230, CYS220, GLU221, PRO222, PRO153, PRO152, THR150, GLY154, THR155, PRO151, PRO223. The dimensions of the grid box as follows center_x = 95.80Å; center_y = 91.94Å; center_z = -44.74Å; size_x = 26.33Å; size_y = 22.54Å; size_z = 20.14Å with a exhaustiveness of 8. Finally, the docking was initiated by selecting the run Vina option from the pyrx terminal.

Molecular Dynamics

The Molecular Dynamics simulations for the protein-ligand complexes were executed using the GROMACS software package [42]. Initially, the docked protein-ligand complex was separated into its constituent protein and ligand using Pymol [43]. Docked protein-ligand complexes were separated into individual molecules using PyMOL for further analysis. Protein topology was generated with the Amber99sb-ildn force field in GROMACS. Ligand topology was generated using ACPYPE [44-45]. Protein and ligand topologies were then merged to create a complex topology for MD simulations. The prepared system was solvated using a dodecahedron with TIP3P water model and neutralized with NaCl ions. The prepared system underwent energy minimization for 1000 steps and 1ns equilibrated at a temperature of 300K during the NVT phase, followed by NPT equilibration at 1 bar pressure, utilizing MDP file from the Lekumal protein-ligand MD simulation tutorial [46]. The equilibrated system was then subjected to MD simulation for duration of 100 nanoseconds, the results saved in a trajectory file (XTC). The hydrogen bond analysis has been carried out using VMD software [47].

III.RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. In-vitro studies of Chalcone compounds

Anti-bacterial activity

Antibacterial activity of BDP and BMP reveals distinct profiles against the two bacterial strains. Against *E. coli*, chalcone BMP is the more effective agent. While both compounds become active only at higher concentrations, BMP demonstrates a superior dose-dependent response, with its zone of inhibition increasing from 11 mm at 75 µl to 13 mm at 100 µl. In contrast, BDP's activity against *E. coli* plateaus at 11 mm from 75 µl onwards. Conversely, against *S. aureus*, BDP emerges as the more potent antibacterial agent. It is effective at a lower concentration of 75 µl, producing a 12 mm zone of inhibition, whereas BMP only shows activity at the highest tested concentration of 100 µl, yielding a similar 12 mm zone. This indicates that BDP requires a lower dose to achieve the same level of efficacy as BMP against *S. aureus*. Overall, the choice between BDP and BMP as an antibacterial agent is organism-specific: BMP is more effective against *E. coli*, while BDP is more potent against *S. aureus*. Table 1 shows the Antibacterial activity of BDP and BMP against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*. The results are measured by the zone of inhibition in millimeters (mm), where a larger zone indicates greater antibacterial effectiveness shown in Figure 1 and 2.

Table 1: Antibacterial activity of BDP and BMP Against *E.coli* and *S.aureus*

Name of strain	Sample Code	Zone of inhibition (mm) Concentration (µl)				Control
		25	50	75	100	
<i>E. coli</i>	BDP	0	0	11	11	20
<i>S. aureus</i>		0	0	12	11	
<i>E. coli</i>	BMP	0	0	11	13	20
<i>S. aureus</i>		0	0	0	12	

Figure 1: BDP: (a) *E.coli* (b) *S. aureus*

Figure 2: BMP: (a) E.coli (b) S. aureus

Anti-fungal activity

BDP and BMP reveals that both compounds exhibit antifungal activity against *C. albicans*, with varying degrees of effectiveness. Chalcone BDP demonstrated a slightly higher potency, showing an inhibitory effect (a 10 mm zone of inhibition) at a concentration of 75 μ l. This activity increased in a dose-dependent manner to 11 mm at the highest concentration of 100 μ l. In contrast, chalcone BMP only exhibited antifungal activity at the maximum concentration tested, producing a 10 mm zone of inhibition at 100 μ l (Figure 3). This suggests that BDP is a more potent antifungal agent than BMP, as it is effective at a lower concentration and achieves a marginally larger zone of inhibition at the highest dose Table 2 shows the antifungal activity of two chalcone compounds, BDP and BMP, against the fungus *Candida albicans*.

**Table 2: Anti-fungal activity of Chalcone BDP and BMP
Against *C.albicans***

Name of strain	Sample Code	Zone of inhibition (mm) Concentration (μ l)				Control
		25	50	75	100	
<i>C.albicans</i>	BDP	0	0	10	11	15
	BMP	0	0	0	10	15

Figure 3: Antifungal activity of Chalcone BDP& BMP

MTT assay:

The present study evaluated the cytotoxic potential of two chalcone derivatives, BDP and BMP, against the human breast adenocarcinoma cell line (MDA-MB-231). Our findings clearly demonstrate that both compounds possess significant anti-proliferative activity. The core results of the MTT assay revealed a clear concentration-dependent reduction in cell viability for both chalcones. This effect was quantitatively substantiated by their potent IC_{50} values: BDP at $52.94 \pm 0.96 \mu\text{M}$ and BMP at $53.30 \pm 0.97 \mu\text{M}$. These values are remarkably similar, suggesting that both compounds have a comparable level of inhibitory activity against MDA-MB-231 cell proliferation. Furthermore, microscopic examination provided compelling evidence of the cytotoxic effect, showing distinct morphological aberrations and a significant decrease in cell numbers in the treated groups compared to the untreated control shown in Figure 4 & 5. These visual observations verify the quantitative data from the MTT assay, confirming the compounds' ability to induce cellular damage and inhibit growth. As a result, BDP and BMP are promising cytotoxic agents that effectively inhibit the growth of MDA-MB-231 breast cancer cells. Their potent and comparable IC_{50} values warrant further investigation into their mechanisms of action and potential as lead compounds for the development of novel anti-cancer therapies.

Figure 4: Cell proliferation of BDP against the MDA-MB-231

Figure 5: Cell proliferation of BMP against the MDA-MB-231

B. *In-silico* studies of Chalcone compounds

SWISS ADME

The *in-silico* ADME (absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion) properties of two compounds, BDP and BMP predicted using the SWISS ADME tool. These properties provide valuable insights into the potential pharmacological profiles of the compounds and their suitability as drug candidates shown in Figure 6 and Table 3. BDP shows moderate predicted water solubility and high gastrointestinal (GI) absorption, suggesting good oral bioavailability despite being a P-gp substrate. Its bioavailability score is estimated at 0.55. BMP also has a moderate bioavailability score of 0.55 and good GI absorption, suggesting potential for oral bioavailability. The calculated Log P values for BMP indicate good lipophilicity, which is often associated with favorable membrane permeability and oral absorption. Both BDP and BMP adhere to Lipinski's rule of five and other drug-likeness rules (Ghose, Veber, Egan, Muegge), indicating a high probability of being orally bioavailable. Both compounds have favorable lead-likeness scores, suggesting they are potential starting points for medicinal chemistry optimization. Neither compound has alerts for pan-assay interference compounds (PAINS). BDP has one alert for a Michael acceptor, which indicates potential reactivity. In contrast, BMP has one Brenk alert with a single violation in lead-likeness, which further supports its potential as a lead compound. A key difference lies in their predicted distribution properties. BDP is predicted to not permeate the blood-brain barrier (BBB). Equally, BMP is predicted to have BBB permeability, which suggests potential for central nervous system (CNS) activity. Both compounds are predicted to inhibit several cytochrome P450 (CYP) enzymes, raising concerns about potential drug-drug interactions. Specifically, BDP is flagged as an inhibitor of CYP1A2, CYP2C9, CYP2C19, CYP2D6, and CYP3A4. BMP is predicted to inhibit CYP1A2, CYP2C19, and CYP2C9. Both compounds have reasonable synthetic accessibility scores. BDP has a score of 2.77, while BMP has a slightly higher score of 2.87.

[Pink area in plotted graph represents favorable properties for excellent oral bioavailability. LIPO (Lipophilicity), XLOGP between -0.7 and $+5.0$, SIZE (Molecular weight and range = 150 to 500 g/mol), POLAR (Polarity), TPSA (20 and 130), INSOLU (Solubility), Log S not higher than 6, INSATU (Saturation), FLEX (Flexibility), and no more than 10 rotatable bond]

Figure 6: Bioavailability radar charts of Chalcone BDP and BMP

Table 3: Physiochemical properties of Chalcones

Parameters	BDP	BMP
RB	5	3
HBA	3	2
HBD	0	0
TPSA	35.53	30.21
BBB permeant/GI Absorption	Yes/High	Yes/High
Log P	4.00	3.63
Log S	-4.81	-4.37
Lipinski/ violation	Yes/0	Yes/0
Water Solubility	Moderate	Moderate
Bioavailability score	0.55	0.55

[The parameters are stand as such RB, number of rotatable bonds; HBA, number of hydrogen bond acceptors; HBD, number of hydrogen bond donors; TPSA, topological polar surface area; Log P, lipophilicity ; Log S, water solubility; Lipinski violations, Bioavailability score]

The reasonable synthetic accessibility for both compounds makes them promising candidates for further structural exploration and biological evaluation. Both BDP and BMP show promising in silico ADME properties, adhering to key drug-likeness and lead-likeness rules.

Molecular Docking

The Molecular Docking studies for BDP and BMP with the TP53 enzyme (PDB ID: 3ZME) reveals several key differences and similarities shown in Figure 7 -10. The TP53 protein, often called the "guardian of the genome," plays a critical role in preventing cancer by repairing DNA damage or initiating programmed cell death. Mutations in this protein, which are common in breast cancer, can lead to uncontrolled cell growth and a poorer prognosis. Therefore, molecules that can stabilize the mutant TP53 protein are of great therapeutic interest. In the docking experiments, both compounds showed strong binding affinity, with BDP having a slightly more favorable score of -6.9 Kcal/mol compared to BMP's -6.8 Kcal/mol. This suggests that BDP may have a marginally stronger predicted binding to the active site. While both compounds interact with the same total number of 12 active site residues, the types of interactions and the specific residues involved in each type vary. The nature of these interactions is crucial for stable binding. Van der Waals interactions, which arise from temporary electron fluctuations, are typically weak but cumulatively provide significant stability. Pi-alkyl and Pi-sigma interactions are non-covalent forces involving aromatic rings and alkyl groups, which are vital for molecular recognition and contributing to binding affinity. BDP exhibits a broader range of interaction types, including Van der Waals, Pi-sigma, Pi-Alkyl, and a unique, weak pi-sulfur interaction with CYS (A) 220. This specific

interaction, involving the pi-electron cloud of an aromatic ring and the sulfur atom of the cysteine residue, highlights a unique binding mechanism for BDP. In contrast, BMP's interactions are limited to Pi-Alkyl, Alkyl, and Van der Waals. Although both compounds share many interacting residues, such as VAL (A) 147 and PHE (A) 109, BMP also engages with residues like ASP (A) 148 and SER (A) 149 listed in Table 4. This suggests that while their binding pockets overlap, the specific orientation and contact points within the active site are distinct.

Figure 7: 3D Interaction of BDP With 3ZME

Figure 8: 2D Interaction of Compound BDP With 3ZME

Figure 9: 3D Interaction of BDP With 3ZME

Figure 10: 2D Interaction of BMP With 3ZME

Table 4: Shows the Interaction between the compounds and TP53***All the active site residues were bolded**

S.No	Name	Binding Affinity (Kcal/Mol)	Type of Interaction	Amino acids involved in the interaction	Van der Waals
1.	BDP with TP53 (3ZME)	-6.9	Pi-sigma	VAL(A) 147	GLU (A) 221, VAL (A) 157, THR (A) 230, SER (A) 227, GLY (A) 226, GLU (A) 224, VAL (A) 225, THR (A) 150
			Pi-Alkyl and Alkyl	LEU (A) 145, LEU (A) 257, PHE (A) 109, PRO (A) 222, PRO (A) 223, PRO (A) 151	
			Pi-sulfur	CYS (A) 220	
2.	BMP with TP53 (3ZME)	-6.8	Pi-Alkyl and Alkyl	PRO (A) 151, CYS (A) 220, PHE (A) 109, LEU (A) 145, LEU (A) 257, VAL (A) 147	ASP (A) 148, SER (A) 149, ASP (A) 228, THR (A) 150, PRO (A) 223, PRO (A) 222, VAL (A) 157, GLU (A) 221, THR (A) 230

Finally, both BDP and BMP are predicted to bind effectively to the mutant TP53 protein and are considered potential candidates for breast cancer treatment. However, their specific therapeutic roles may differ. The docking study for BMP explicitly suggests it acts as a stabilizer for the mutant TP53 form, which is a key strategy for restoring the protein's tumor-suppressing function. BDP's strong binding and diverse interactions also point to its potential as a therapeutic agent, possibly by a similar or a different stabilizing mechanism. These differences in interaction profiles provide valuable insights into how each compound might function at a molecular level.

Molecular Dynamics:

Root Mean Square Deviation and Root Mean Square Fluctuation Analysis

The conformational and structural variations of the complex during the MD simulation were analyzed using two analyses: Root Mean Square Deviation (RMSD) and Root Mean Square Fluctuation (RMSF). The RMSD evaluates the degree to which the complex deviates from its initial structure over time. RMSF determines the fluctuation of each residue in the complex. Calculations of the RMSDs were carried out for TP53, synthesized compound, and TP53-synthesized compound complex for BDP and BMP and are shown in Figure 11a & b and 12a & b as a graph. The average RMSD of the TP53-synthesized compound complex was 0.96nm and 0.89nm for BDP and BMP respectively. The fluctuation of each residue in the complex was analyzed and shown as graph.

Figure 11a

Figure 11b

Figure 12b

Figure 12a

Radius of Gyration and Solvent Accessible Surface Area Analysis

The folded state of a protein was considered to be an essential part of biological processes. as the function of the protein is determined by its folding state. Using the Radius of Gyration (RG), the compactness of the protein structure was assessed. The protein's folding throughout the simulation was assessed using this compactness. The average RG for the TP53-synthesized compound complex was 1.68 nm for both the compounds. The Solvent Accessible Surface Area (SASA) is an important parameter used to measure the surface area of the protein and ligand accessible to the solvent. SASA provides insights into the structural stability, folding, and interactions between the protein and ligand. Changes in SASA during the simulation can indicate a binding event, conformational change, or exposure of hydrophobic or hydrophilic regions, contributing to a better understanding of the dynamics and behavior of the protein-ligand complex. The average SASA for the TP53-synthesized compound complex was 107.60nm²and 109.4 nm²for BDP and BMP. Both RG and SASA has been plotted in the graph for BDP and BMP shown in Figure 11 c & 3d and 12 c & d.

Radius of gyration

Figure 11c

Solvent Accessible Surface

Figure 11d

Radius of gyration

Figure 12c

Solvent Accessible Surface

Figure 12d

Molecular Mechanics Poisson-Boltzmann Surface Area (MMPBSA) and Hydrogen Bond Analysis

The Molecular Mechanics Poisson-Boltzmann Surface Area (MMPBSA) results show that both BDP and BMP form stable complexes with the TP53 enzyme, as evidenced by their negative binding energies. BDP's binding energy is more favorable at -92.804 ± 11.917 kJ/mol, compared to BMP's -91.783 ± 10.392 kJ/mol. This difference is primarily driven by BDP's stronger van der Waals energy (-164.077 kJ/mol) and electrostatic energy (-19.509 kJ/mol), which are both more negative than BMP's van der Waals energy (-152.601 kJ/mol) and electrostatic energy (-12.160 kJ/mol). However, both compounds exhibit positive polar solvation energy, with BDP's being significantly higher (106.998 kJ/mol) than BMP's (86.480 kJ/mol), which disfavors binding but is overcome by the other stabilizing forces. The SASA energy for BDP (-16.215 kJ/mol) is also more favorable than that of BMP (-13.503 kJ/mol).

Figure 12e

The Hydrogen Bond Analysis further highlights the differences in the stability and specificity of the protein-ligand interactions shown in Figure 11e & 12e. BDP forms repeated hydrogen bonds with SER227 and GLY226 residues, demonstrating high occupancy percentages of 56.99% and 44.91%, respectively. In contrast, BMP forms hydrogen bonds with different residues, PRO151 and CYS220, and these bonds are significantly less persistent, with occupancy percentages of only 21.26% and 15.17%. This indicates that while both compounds form stable complexes, BDP's interaction with the TP53 active site is characterized by more frequent and stable hydrogen bonding, which contributes to its overall higher binding affinity and complex stability. Based on this analyses, the study concludes that the synthesized compound (BDP) forms a more stable and favorable complex with the TP53 protein compared to the other compound (BMP). This is primarily due to its stronger binding energy and more stable hydrogen bonding interactions. The relevance of this finding to anti-cancer activity lies in the TP53 protein's critical role as a tumor suppressor.

IV. CONCLUSION

Chalcone derivatives BDP and BMP demonstrated significant in-vitro biological activity, exhibiting both potent antimicrobial effects against various bacterial and fungal strains and notable cytotoxicity against the MDA-MB-231 breast cancer cell line. Mechanistic studies, including molecular docking and dynamics simulations, predicted that the anticancer activity stems from a strong binding affinity to the TP53 protein. This finding is highly significant, suggesting that BDP and BMP may act by stabilizing or reactivating the mutated TP53 tumor suppressor protein, thereby potentially restoring DNA repair or inducing apoptosis in cancer cells. Favorable pharmacokinetic properties predicted by SWISSADME further support their potential as drug candidates. Consequently, these results position BDP and BMP as lead compounds for breast cancer therapy. Future work will focus on structural modifications to optimize their pharmacological profile, enhance anticancer potency, and improve cancer cell selectivity.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

MH (Madhukar Hemamalini) thank the SERB-IRE for financial support – Ref. No.SIR/2022/000011. ACP (Anaglit Catherine Paul) thanks the Mother Teresa Women's University, Tamil Nadu, India, for financial support.

REFERENCES

- [1] Fadeyi, O. O., Adamson, S. T., Myles, E. L., & Okoro, C. O. (2008). Novel fluorinated acridone derivatives. Part 1: Synthesis and evaluation as potential anticancer agents. *Bioorganic & Medicinal Chemistry Letters*, 18(14), 4172–4176. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bmcl.2008.05.101>
- [2] Rostom, S. A. F. (2006). Synthesis and in vitro antitumor evaluation of some indeno[1,2-c]pyrazol(in)es substituted with sulfonamide, sulfonyleurea(-thiourea) pharmacophores, and some derived thiazole ring systems. *Bioorganic & Medicinal Chemistry*, 14(19), 6475–6485. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bmc.2006.06.014>
- [3] Patel, K., Karthikeyan, C., Solomon, V. R., Hari Narayana Moorthy, N. S., Lee, H., Sahu, K., Deora, G. S., & Trivedi, P. (2011). Synthesis of some coumarinyl chalcones and their antiproliferative activity against breast cancer cell lines. *Letters in Drug Design & Discovery*, 8(4), 308–311. <https://doi.org/10.2174/157018011794839441>
- [4] Hsu, Y. L., Kuo, P. L., Tzeng, W. S., & Lin, C. C. (2006). Chalcone inhibits the proliferation of human breast cancer cells by blocking cell cycle progression and inducing apoptosis. *Food and Chemical Toxicology*, 44(5), 704–713. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fct.2005.10.003>
- [5] Baselga, J., & Mendelsohn, J. (1994). The epidermal growth factor receptor as a target for therapy in breast carcinoma. *Breast Cancer Research and Treatment*, 29(1), 127–138. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00666187>
- [6] Bandgar, B. P., Gawande, S. S., Bodade, R. G., Totre, J. V., & Khobragade, C. N. (2010). Synthesis and biological evaluation of simple methoxylated chalcones as anticancer, anti-inflammatory and antioxidant agents. *Bioorganic & Medicinal Chemistry*, 18(3), 1364–1370. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bmc.2009.12.034>
- [7] Martirosyan, A., Rahim-Bata, R., Freeman, A., Clarke, C., Howard, R., & Strobl, J. (2004). Differentiation-inducing quinolines as experimental breast cancer agents in the MCF-7 human cancer cell model. *Biochemical Pharmacology*, 68(9), 1729–1738.
- [8] Mól, W., Matyja, M., Filip, B., & Wietrzyk, S. (2008). Synthesis and antiproliferative activity in vitro of novel (2-butynyl)thioquinolines. *Bioorganic & Medicinal Chemistry*, 16(17), 8136–8141.
- [9] Hu, L., Jiang, J.-D., Qu, J., Li, Y., Jin, J., Li, Z.-R., & Boykin, D. W. (2007). Novel potent antimetabolic heterocyclic ketones: Synthesis, antiproliferative activity, and structure–activity relationships. *Bioorganic & Medicinal Chemistry Letters*, 17(13), 3613–3617.
- [10] Issa, S., Walchshofer, N., Kassab, I., Termoss, H., Chamat, S., Geahchan, A., & Bouaziz, Z. (2010). Synthesis and antiproliferative activity of oxazinocarbazole and N,N-bis(carbazolylmethyl)amine derivatives. *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 45(6), 2567–2577.
- [11] Hadjidakou, S. K., & Hadjiladis, N. (2009). Antiproliferative and anti-tumor activity of organotin compounds. *Coordination Chemistry Reviews*, 253(1-2), 235–249.
- [12] Solomon, V. R., Hu, C., & Lee, H. (2010). Design and synthesis of chloroquine analogs with anti-breast cancer property. *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 45(9), 3916–3923.
- [13] Solomon, V. R., Hu, C., & Lee, H. (2009). Hybrid pharmacophore design and synthesis of isatin-benzothiazole analogs for their anti-breast cancer activity. *Bioorganic & Medicinal Chemistry*, 17(21), 7585–7592.
- [14] Solomon, V. R., Hu, C., & Lee, H. (2010). Design and synthesis of anti-breast cancer agents from 4-piperazinylquinoline: A hybrid pharmacophore approach. *Bioorganic & Medicinal Chemistry*, 18(4), 1563–1572.
- [15] Agrawal, P. K. (Ed.). (1989). *Carbon-13 NMR of flavonoids*. Elsevier Science Publishers B.V.
- [16] Begum, N. A., Roy, N., Laskar, R. A., & Roy, K. (2010). Mosquito larvicidal studies of some chalcone analogues and their derived products: Structure–activity relationship analysis. *Medicinal Chemistry Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00044-010-9305-6>
- [17] Go, M. L., Wu, X., & Liu, X. L. (2005). Chalcones: An update on cytotoxic and hemoprotective properties. *Current Medicinal Chemistry*, 12(4), 481–499.
- [18] Chimentì, F., Fioravanti, R., Bolasco, A., Chimentì, P., Secci, D., Rossi, R., Yáñez, M., Orallo, F., Ortuso, F., & Alcaro, S. (2009). Chalcones: A valid scaffold for monoamine oxidase inhibitors. *Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 52(9), 2818–2824.
- [19] Liu, M., Wilairat, P., & Go, M. L. (2001). Antimalarial alkoxyated and hydroxyated chalcones: Structure–activity relationship analysis. *Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 44(25), 4443–4452.
- [20] Ducki, S., Forrest, R., Hadfield, J. A., Kendall, A., Lawrence, N. J., McGown, A. T., & Rennison, D. (1998). Potent antimetabolic and cell growth inhibitory properties of substituted chalcones. *Bioorganic & Medicinal Chemistry Letters*, 8(9), 1051–1056.
- [21] Bois, F., Boumendjel, A., Mariotte, A., Conseil, G., & Di Pietro, A. (1999). Synthesis and biological activity of 4-alkoxychalcones: Potential hydrophobic modulators of P-glycoprotein-mediated multidrug resistance. *Bioorganic & Medicinal Chemistry*, 7(12), 2691–2695.
- [22] Dimmock, J. R., Elias, D. W., Beazely, M. A., & Kandepu, N. M. (1999). Bioactivities of chalcones. *Current Medicinal Chemistry*, 6(12), 1125–1149.
- [23] Hsu, Y. L., Kuo, P. L., Chiang, L. C., & Lin, C. C. (2004). Isoliquiritigenin inhibits the proliferation and induces the apoptosis of human non-small cell lung cancer A549 cells. *Clinical and Experimental Pharmacology and Physiology*, 31(7), 414–418.
- [24] Fu, Y., Hsieh, T. C., Guo, J., Kunicki, J., Lee, M. Y., Darzynkiewicz, Z., & Wu, J. M. (2004). Licochalcone-A, a novel flavonoid isolated from licorice root (*Glycyrrhiza glabra*), causes G2 and late-G1 arrests in androgen-independent PC-3 prostate cancer cells. *Biochemical and Biophysical Research Communications*, 322(1), 263–270.
- [25] Zi, X., & Simoneau, A. R. (2005). Flavokawain A, a novel chalcone from kava extract, induces apoptosis in bladder cancer cells by involvement of Bax protein-dependent and mitochondria-dependent apoptotic pathway and suppresses tumor growth in mice. *Cancer Research*, 65(8), 3479–3486.
- [26] Tabata, K., Motani, K., Takayanagi, N., Nishimura, R., Asami, S., Kimura, Y., Ukiya, M., Hasegawa, D., Akihisa, T., & Suzuki, T. (2005). Xanthoangelol, a major chalcone constituent of *Angelica keiskei*, induces apoptosis in neuroblastoma and leukemia cells. *Biological and Pharmaceutical Bulletin*, 28(8), 1404–1407.
- [27] Takahashi, T. T., Takasuka, N., Ligo, M., Baba, M., Nishino, H., Tsuda, H., & Okuyama, T. (2004). Isoliquiritigenin, a flavonoid from licorice, reduces prostaglandin E2 and nitric oxide, causes apoptosis, and suppresses aberrant crypt foci development. *Cancer Science*, 95(5), 448–453.
- [28] Samoszuk, M., Tan, J., & Chorn, G. (2005). The chalcone butein from *Rhus verniciflua* Stokes inhibits clonogenic growth of human breast cancer cells co-cultured with fibroblasts. *BMC Complementary and Alternative Medicine*, 5, Article 5. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6882-5-5>
- [29] Sharma, A., Chakravarti, B., Gupta, M. P., Siddiqui, J. A., Konwar, R., & Tripathi, R. P. (2010). Synthesis and anti-breast cancer activity of biphenyl-based chalcones. *Bioorganic & Medicinal Chemistry*, 18(13), 4711–4720.
- [30] Liu, X. L., Tee, H. W., & Go, M. L. (2008). Functionalized chalcones as selective inhibitors of P-glycoprotein and breast cancer resistance protein. *Bioorganic & Medicinal Chemistry*, 16(1), 171–180.
- [31] Moorthy, N. S. H. N., Karthikeyan, C., & Trivedi, P. (2009). Synthesis, cytotoxic evaluation and in silico pharmacokinetic prediction of some benzo[a]phenazine-5-sulfonic acid derivatives. *Medicinal Chemistry*, 5(6), 549–557.
- [32] Moorthy, N. S. H. N., Karthikeyan, C., & Trivedi, P. (2010). Design, synthesis, cytotoxic evaluation and QSAR study of some 6H-indolo[2,3-b]quinoxaline derivatives. *Journal of Enzyme Inhibition and Medicinal Chemistry*, 25(3), 394–405.
- [33] Nehru, J., Chakkarapani, N., Rajakannan, V., Savaridasson, J. K., Amutha, T., Uma Maheshwari, S., & Hemamalini, M. (2023). [Title of article not provided]. *Journal of Molecular Structure*, 1286, Article 135591.
- [34] Daina, A., Michielin, O., & Zoete, V. (2017). SwissADME: A free web tool to evaluate pharmacokinetics, drug-likeness and medicinal chemistry friendliness of small molecules. *Scientific Reports*, 7, Article 42717.

- [35] Pires, D. E. V., Blundell, T. L., & Ascher, D. B. (2015). pkCSM: Predicting small-molecule pharmacokinetic and toxicity properties using graph-based signatures. *Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 58(9), 4066–4072.
- [36] Domínguez-Villa, F. X., Durán-Iturbide, N. A., & Ávila-Zárraga, J. G. (2021). Synthesis, molecular docking, and in silico ADME/Tox profiling studies of new 1-aryl-5-(3-azidopropyl)indol-4-ones: Potential inhibitors of SARS-CoV-2 main protease. *Bioorganic Chemistry*, 106, Article 104497.
- [37] Liu, X., Wilcken, R., Joerger, A. C., Chuckowree, I. S., Amin, J., Spencer, J., & Fersht, A. R. (2013). Small molecule induced reactivation of mutant p53 in cancer cells. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 41(12), 6034–6044. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkt305>
- [38] Durga, B., & Julius, A. (2020). In silico docking studies of thymoquinone as a potential anti-cancer drug target on lung cancer cells. *European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine*, 7(11), 1706–1716.
- [39] Schrödinger, L., & DeLano, W. (2020). PyMOL (Version 2.x) [Computer software]. <https://www.pymol.org/pymol>
- [40] Goodsell, D. S., & Olson, A. J. (1990). Automated docking of substrates to proteins by simulated annealing. *Proteins: Structure, Function, and Genetics*, 8(3), 195–202.
- [41] Trott, O., & Olson, A. J. (2010). AutoDock Vina: Improving the speed and accuracy of docking with a new scoring function, efficient optimization, and multithreading. *Journal of Computational Chemistry*, 31(2), 455–461. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jcc.21334>
- [42] Bekker, H., Berendsen, H. J. C., Dijkstra, E. J., Achterop, S., van Drunen, R., van der Spoel, D., Sijbers, A., Keegstra, H., & Renardus, M. K. R. (1993). GROMACS—A parallel computer for molecular dynamics simulations. In *Proceedings of the 4th International Conference on Computational Physics (PC 92)* (pp. 252–256). World Scientific Publishing.
- [43] Schrödinger, L., & DeLano, W. (2020). PyMOL (Version 2.x) [Computer software]. <https://www.pymol.org/pymol>
- [44] Sousa da Silva, A. W., & Vranken, W. F. (2012). ACPYPE—AnteChamber PYthon Parser interfacE. *BMC Research Notes*, 5, Article 367.
- [45] Kagami, L. P., Sousa da Silva, A. W., Díaz, A., & Vranken, W. F. (n.d.). The ACPYPE web server for small molecule MD topology generation. Manuscript submitted for publication.
- [46] Lemkul, J. A. (2018). From proteins to perturbed Hamiltonians: A suite of tutorials for the GROMACS-2018 molecular simulation package. *Living Journal of Computational Molecular Science*, 1(1), Article 33011.
- [47] Humphrey, W., Dalke, A., & Schulten, K. (1996). VMD: Visual molecular dynamics. *Journal of Molecular Graphics*, 14(1), 33–38.